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Exploring global, economy-wide material trajectories and associated environmental pressures under shared socioeconomic pathways

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E-mail: tommi.ekholm@fmi.fi**Keywords:** material flow analysis, integrated assessment model, shared socio-economic pathways, scenariosSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)**Abstract**

Material production is a major contributor to many environmental challenges, but has received limited attention in the global, long-term scenarios produced by integrated assessment models (IAMs) used to investigate humankind's potential responses. Here, we quantify economy-wide material stocks and flows for the shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) and a low material demand scenario (LMD) using a simplified but physically consistent approach developed to the SuCCESs IAM, based on empirically observed material stock intensities of the global economy and the detailed, economy-wide stock-flow modelling of MISO2. Demand for material stocks is then translated to the material production, recycling and final waste disposal flows, parametrized from the MISO2 model. Implications for energy use, CO₂ emissions, land use and human appropriation of net primary production are quantified via the SuCCESs IAM. We find that economy-wide material stocks grow substantially in all scenarios between 2020 and 2100—from +55% in LMD, to a nine-fold increase in SSP5. Stabilization or gradual reduction of material production and related environmental pressures only occur when low economic growth is combined with strong decoupling of GDP from material stocks. Material production volumes of major materials, e.g. steel and concrete, grow in all scenarios except LMD. Without active mitigation, the environmental impacts from material production continue to increase in all but the SSP3 and LMD scenarios, in which the impacts remain stable or decline even without deliberate action to reduce them. Conversely, with moderately or strongly growing GDP and only slightly declining material stock intensity, material production would grow immensely, requiring significant effort to mitigate the related environmental pressures. Waste accumulation will continue to grow for at least several decades due to the inherent lag in material flow dynamics.

1. Introduction

Material production is a major contributor to environmental pressures. It requires 37% of global primary energy supply (Krausmann *et al* 2020), is responsible for 23%–35% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Hertwich 2021, Lamb *et al* 2021); a notable contributor to human appropriation of primary biomass production (Haberl *et al* 2014); and the sole reason

for the mining of raw materials and waste accumulation (Krausmann *et al* 2017b, Schandl *et al* 2018). From climate change and GHG emission perspective, it is one of the 'hard to abate' sectors (Edelenbosch *et al* 2024). Hence, considering material production is crucial when exploring pathways towards a sustainable society. However, so far this has mainly been done for specific materials or sectors, while economy-wide approaches consistently covering materials

flows and stocks across the global economy are lacking.

Scenarios of long-term sustainability transitions, particularly for climate change mitigation, are often envisioned through the shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) (O'Neill *et al* 2017, Riahi *et al* 2017). The SSPs comprise five storylines that reflect varying degrees of difficulty in achieving effective climate change mitigation and adaptation. These are further quantified through projections of population change, economic growth, and to different sectors, such as energy (Bauer *et al* 2017) and land-use (Popp *et al* 2017). Overall, the SSPs are meant to facilitate evidence synthesis across studies, as each group utilizes the same underlying narratives and drivers.

Yet, comprehensive, economy-wide quantifications on material flows and stocks across the SSPs are limited. We are aware of only one peer-reviewed study that quantifies economy-wide flows of raw materials for the SSPs: Schandl *et al* (2020) used the computable general equilibrium model GTEM-C and extended the underlying input–output tables by raw material extraction per sector, without tracing the entire life cycle of materials, product stocks and waste flows. Studies quantifying both flows and stocks of a single material across the SSPs were conducted for plastics (Stegmann *et al* 2022), or steel (Kermeli *et al* 2022). Sectoral analyses are available e.g. for global buildings (Deetman *et al* 2020) and the energy system (Ünlü *et al* 2024) for the middle-of-the-road SSP2 scenario. Subsequently, there is a major research gap regarding the biophysically consistent modelling of economy-wide material flows and product stocks in integrated assessment models (IAMs), which is necessary to fully explore thermodynamically possible as well as socially desirable futures (Pauliuk *et al* 2017, Wiedenhofer *et al* 2024b, Magalar *et al* 2026).

The key question we therefore want to address herein is what kinds of pathways of economy-wide material stocks can be imagined within the SSP framework, and how much material production and subsequent energy use and GHG emissions would be required. This requires developing new modelling approaches and scenario parametrizations.

For this purpose, we present a novel stock-flow-consistent materials module for the SuCCESs IAM (Ekholm *et al* 2025), with which we systematically quantify economy-wide material stocks and flows for the SSPs, consistently covering material production, product stocks, waste and recycling; and their impact on energy use, land-use, CO₂ emissions and waste accumulation. The novel stock-flow-consistent materials module is parametrized based on the state-of-the-art dynamic, inflow-driven material stock-flow model MISO2 (Wiedenhofer *et al* 2024a). Compared to prior literature, we quantify both stocks

and flows through materials' entire life cycle, instead of only raw material extraction (Schandl *et al* 2020); and for the whole economy, instead of only for a single material or sector (Deetman *et al* 2020, Kermeli *et al* 2022, Stegmann *et al* 2022, Ünlü *et al* 2024).

However, while the SSPs span a broad range of alternative futures, they all project a considerably growing economic output between 2020 and 2100: roughly threefold increase in the low-growth SSP3, and over eightfold in the high-growth SSP5 (IIASA 2024). Under business-as-usual development for material stock intensity, this would imply strongly increasing material stocks and production. This limited span was identified already when the SSPs were crafted (O'Neill *et al* 2017), which prompted calls to also explore low- and post-growth scenarios which achieve high wellbeing with lower demand for energy and materials (Hickel *et al* 2021, Sugiyama *et al* 2024, Edwards *et al* 2025). To address this gap, we construct a scenario of low material demand (LMD) with substantially lower material stock intensity of the economy. Through this first attempt at an LMD scenario, we aim to expand the range of scenarios and improve our understanding of future imaginaries.

The scenarios are quantified with a novel top-down approach, starting from two important empirical observations. Firstly, global material stocks have exhibited strong, long-term coupling with global GDP (Krausmann *et al* 2017a). Secondly, material stock dynamics serve as a much better—and also physically consistent—predictor of material demand than the widely used material production intensity approach (Kermeli *et al* 2022). Our approach thus uses future material stock intensity projections, based on historical observations and scenario narratives, to determine the global material stock, which is then broken down by end-use and further translated into material production, raw material extraction and waste flows through material balance equations.

This novel modelling approach and scenario parametrizations are then used to investigate the entailed environmental pressures across the different scenarios, specifically by using the SuCCESs IAM to link the estimated material production for each scenario to energy use, CO₂ emissions, and land use as well as human appropriation of net primary production (HANPP) (Ekholm *et al* 2025). To isolate the impact of the material system towards these measures, we assume no other changes across the scenarios, e.g. for transportation or food demand. Additionally, we impose no active intervention or mitigation of these environmental pressures, although allowing for autonomous improvements due to the model's optimization approach; and investigate their magnitude in the different storylines and quantifications of the SSP scenarios.

2. Methods

For calculating the future stocks and flows of materials, we developed to the SuCCESs IAM a novel material module, which is a simplified, global-level representation of the MISO2 model. An overview of this is presented in figure 1. MISO2 covers 14 supply chain processes from raw material extraction and processing, stock-building and stock dynamics, to end-of-life (EoL) flows and waste management, for 23 raw materials and 20 stock-building materials across 177 countries from 1900 to 2016. The SuCCESs material module covers the same stocks and flows on the global level, and models explicitly the production technologies of concrete, steel, aluminium, copper, nickel, plastic, paper, board and wood. More detailed descriptions of both models and the SuCCESs material module are provided in the supplementary material, enabling the development of similar representations to other models.

Our projections of global, economy-wide material stocks are based on the identity between gross economic output Y_t , total material stock S_t , and material stock intensity η_t (material stock per output) at time t :

$$S_t = \eta_t Y_t. \quad (1)$$

In contrast to an approach connecting economic output and material flows (e.g. production), this relationship appears more sensible based on the historical observations (Haberl *et al* 2019, Kermeli *et al* 2022).

In our quantification, the global material stock modelled with the MISO2 model (Wiedenhofer *et al* 2024a) and economic output based on Bolt and van Zanden (2024) have increased proportionally since the 19th century, with the material stock intensity η_t ranging between 9.0 and 10.8 kg/\$ (in 2017 terms, PPP-adjusted). This is illustrated in figure 2(a) (grey dots).

Given this long-term stability of material stock intensity η_t , we extrapolate this quantity for the SSPs with variations according to the SSP narratives (O'Neill *et al* 2017). These are summarized in table 1. In the ‘middle-of-the-road’ SSP2 and the ‘fragmented’ SSP3, consumption remains material-intensive, which we quantify as η_t remaining at its average of 1900–2016. In the sustainability-oriented SSP1, we extrapolate the decline of η_t from its peak in 1950, reaching 8.1 kg/\$ by 2100. The storyline of SSP4 narrates divergent development between rich and poor, and we assume η_t to decline to its lowest 20th century level by 2100. In contrast, the materialism of the SSP5 ‘fossil-fueled highway’ is quantified with η_t returning to its 20th century peak by 2100. When combined with the SSPs’ GDP projections, these intensity assumptions yield the global material stock, which is presented in figure 2(a).

This range of assumptions for η_t is similar to the ‘BAU low’, ‘BAU high’ and ‘CONV high’ scenarios of Krausmann *et al* (2020), although the transitions happen more slowly in our case (by 2100, instead of 2050 as in Krausmann *et al*). Due to the slower transition and differing GDP projections, our scenarios

Table 1. Scenario storylines regarding material consumption and environmental policy (O'Neill *et al* 2017) and our scenario assumptions for future material stock intensities and recycling rates.

Scenario (SSP)	GDP	Consumption and environmental storyline	Material stock intensity	Recycling rate
Sustainability (SSP1)	SSP1	Low growth in material consumption; improved management of local and global issues	Extrapolated to decline from the 10.8 kg/\$ peak in 1950 to 8.1 kg/\$ in 2100	Significant improvement
Middle of the road (SSP2)	SSP2	Material-intensive consumption; concern for local pollutants, only moderate success in implementation	1900–2016 average (9.7 kg/\$)	Moderate improvement
Regional rivalry (SSP3)	SSP3	Material-intensive consumption; low priority for environment	1900–2016 average (9.7 kg/\$)	Stagnation
Inequality (SSP4)	SSP4	Elites: high consumption lifestyles, rest: low consumption; focus on local environment in medium- and high-income countries	Decline to 20th century minimum by 2100 (9.0 kg/\$)	Moderate improvement
Fossil-fueled development (SSP5)	SSP5	Materialism, status consumption; focus on local environment with obvious benefits to well-being	Increase to 20th century maximum by 2100 (10.8 kg/\$)	Moderate improvement
Low material demand (LMD)	SSP3	Structural break towards low consumption and high recycling of materials	Declines to 50% of 20th century maximum by 2100 (5.4 kg/\$)	Significant improvement

generally involve slightly higher material stocks by 2050.

Additional to the SSPs, we construct a LMD scenario that broadens the scenario ensemble's scope, essentially filling the identified gap of a scenario with low economic growth and high sustainability (O'Neill *et al* 2017). The narrative for this scenario is discussed by Sugiyama *et al* (2024). The LMD scenario assumes the low population growth of SSP1, the low economic growth of SSP3, and material stock intensity that declines to 5.4 kg/\$ by 2100, which is 50% of the observed maximum since 1900. This stock intensity is close to the 'CONV low' scenario of Krausmann *et al* (2020).

Material-specific stocks are calculated in SuCCESs from the total material stock defined by equation (1) by first breaking it down by end-use, then by material, with both end-use shares and end-uses' material shares based on the MISO2 model. The different end-uses' shares in total stock have varied somewhat historically, and we extrapolate this development over the century (figure 2(c)). For material shares in each end-use, we use constant MISO2 default values from 2016. These assumptions are not varied by scenario, as the storylines do not give clear justification for such; but instead, we test the impact of uniform, maximum $\pm 20\%$ relative changes in the end-use and material shares, then normalizing the adjusted shares' sum to one. Please see the supplementary material for details.

By using the stock lifetimes for each end-use and material based on MISO2, SuCCESs calculates the required gross addition to stock (GAS), i.e. how much material input is needed to achieve the projected material stock while accounting for the stocks' EoL depreciation. GAS is then used to calculate the production volume of each modelled material, by using a constant production-to-stock ratio from MISO2 from year 2016, thus accounting for the waste generated at this stage. Total waste generation in SuCCESs includes production waste and the EoL waste. Material-specific recycling rates are extrapolated from MISO2 and differentiated by scenario to three levels of development, as presented in table 1 and the supplementary figure S5. We test the impact of lifetime and recycling rate assumptions similarly as with stock and material shares, please see the supplementary material for details.

SuCCESs, being a demand-driven IAM, is then constrained to satisfy the calculated materials' production volumes each year. No other changes are assumed between the scenarios to isolate the impact of future material production. SuCCESs includes a portfolio of technologies to produce the materials, e.g. blast furnaces and electric arc ovens for steel, which also account for the energy needed and direct emissions from each production process (Ekholm *et al* 2025). The upstream energy flows and emissions, e.g. in oil refining and electricity production, are accounted by their respective processes. The

land-use implications and associated GHG emissions for producing biogenic raw materials, e.g. wood for construction or paper products, are accounted in CLASH (Ekholm *et al* 2024), the land-use module of SuCCESs.

3. Results

We find that with these assumptions, the global material stocks increase considerably during the century across all SSP scenarios, both in absolute (figure 2(a)) and per-capita terms (figure 2(b)). For example, in SSP2 the absolute stock grows fivefold to 6.3 Tt between 2020 and 2100, and the per-capita stock fourfold to 630 t/capita; in SSP5, approximately ninefold in both terms. The assumed, history-based variations of material stock intensity across the SSP scenarios have relatively minor impact, and the level of the stock is mainly determined by the scenarios' GDP development. The 2100 stocks in SSP1 and SSP2, which have similar GDP developments, differ by less than 20%, even as SSP1 extrapolates the decline in intensity from its 1950 peak value.

In contrast, the material stock of the LMD scenario diverges strongly from the SSPs, both in absolute and per-capita terms. The absolute stock in 2100 is 1.9 Tt—i.e. 55% higher than in 2020, but only 55% of the SSP3 scenario, the lowest of the SSPs. The average per-capita stock increases to 240 t in 2100, being only 10% lower than SSP3 due to the differing population projections between the scenarios. We did not assess the distribution of this stock across countries or income groups, which could entail either persisting inequality or relative convergence towards the global average over the century. Nevertheless, the average material stock per capita in the LMD scenario is significantly larger than the estimates on the minimum stock requirements to enable decent living standards for everyone (Vélez-Henao and Pauliuk 2023, Streeck *et al* 2025).

Due to our assumption of continuing the trends for the shares of different end-uses, their stocks grow proportionally to the calculated total stock development (figure 2(c)). Large structures, like buildings, roads and other civil engineering, constitute by far the majority of material stock; with machinery, motor vehicles and other transport equipment comprising the second largest group. The variations applied to the end-use shares in the sensitivity analysis are also apparent in figure 2(c), implying moderate changes in the end-use stocks.

The stocks per material are presented for each scenario in figure 3 (middle column). Given the shares of different end-uses were assumed to remain relatively constant, as shown in figure 2(c), and that each end-uses shares of different materials remains

constant in the scenarios; the materials' stocks differ from each other mostly in their magnitude across the six scenarios.

The production volumes (figure 3, left column) and waste flows (figure 3, right column) develop differently across the considered materials, reflecting the dynamics of end-use stock each material contributes to. The production and waste flows of materials contributing mostly to end-uses with short lifetime (e.g. paper and plastic) follow closely the pattern of stock development, as production needs to constantly replenish the depreciating stock, which leads to the waste flow. Thus, the production and waste flows of these materials are rather directly determined by the GDP and material intensity of each scenario. The variations applied to the end-use shares, material shares lifetimes, and recycling rates have notable impacts on these results, highlighting the major uncertainty in projecting material stocks and flows far into the future. Please see the supplementary material for a more extensive uncertainty analysis.

Stocks with longer lifetime have slower stock-flow dynamics, and hence the production and waste flows of materials that contribute to such stocks (particularly concrete and steel) develop rather differently than their respective stock. Namely, slower stock depreciation implies less EoL waste, which also implies less replacement additions of the material to maintain stock levels. Therefore, concrete waste peaks around 2060 in all scenarios except SSP5. Due to the long lifetimes, the production of concrete (and one of its main constituents, cement) increases only fourfold in the SSP5 scenario, whereas the stock increases nearly tenfold. For the same reason, concrete production declines from 2020 onwards in the LMD scenario to maintain the levelling-off stock in the LMD scenario. The waste flows follow stock additions with a lag. Similar, although more subdued dynamics can be observed with steel.

Figure S4 in the supplementary material presents the production volumes in relation to the scenarios' GDP. The ratio between these two—i.e. the material production intensity—resulting from our stock-based approach develops very differently for different materials. For materials feeding into long-lifetime stocks (concrete, steel and to lesser degree wood), it declines strongly and breaks from the historical trend. This is essentially the same that Kermeli *et al* (2022) observed for steel. Yet, for materials contributing to short-lifetime stocks, the material production intensity follows closely the assumptions for material stock intensity.

Some economy-wide, material-specific scenarios exist in the literature for comparison. For steel, an SSP1 quantification with the IMAGE model (Kermeli *et al* 2022), based on a saturating S-curve fit between per capita steel stocks and GDP per capita, aligns

Figure 2. Global GDP and material stock trajectories, in absolute (a) and in per-capita terms (b), in the considered scenarios until 2100; and stocks per end-use in the MISO simulation for the historical period and the SuCCESs SSP2 scenario (c).

between our LMD and SSP1 scenarios, with the stock stabilizing slightly above 80 Gt in 2100, and with production peaking at 2.3 Gt yr^{-1} around 2050 and then declining to 1.5 Gt yr^{-1} . For cement, the production volumes in 2050 are slightly (-10%) and notably (-27%) lower in the REMIND and IMAGE reference SSP2 scenarios (Soergel *et al* 2024), respectively, than in our SSP2 scenario. For plastics, our production, waste and stocks are somewhat higher (12%–65% in 2100) than the SSP2 quantification with the IMAGE model with plastic demand driven by GDP and population projections (Stegmann *et al* 2022), but exhibit similar dynamics. Given the diversity that exists in modelling approaches and future projections, the method presented here could provide a comprehensive and transparent way to assess future material stocks, as it is based on the identity between GDP and material stocks, and consistent stock-flow accounting to calculate production and waste flows.

If unmitigated, most environmental pressures from material production increase considerably with the projections of higher GDP and material production volume, as presented in figure 4. Domestic extraction, energy use and CO_2 emissions are directly linked with material production and develop much in the same way as production volumes. Domestic extraction, which represents the extracted amount of material inputs, is close to the projections by Schandl *et al* (2020), although our projections slightly are smaller due to some missing components of domestic extraction in our model. As an exception, our quantification for SSP3 is considerably smaller due to the differing assumptions for material intensity in that scenario.

Despite the autonomous improvements in energy efficiency carried out in SuCCESs due to purely economic reasons, energy-use for materials production grows in all of the SSPs, and over six-fold in

the SSP5 scenario from 2020 to 2100; but declines notably in the LMD scenario. The calculated LMD scenario, with 41 EJ yr⁻¹ energy consumption in 2050 for materials' production considered explicitly in SuCCESs could therefore be compatible with the low energy demand scenario with 245 EJ total final energy and 107 EJ industrial energy use (i.e. including more than just stock-building material production)

envisioned by Grubler *et al* (2018). CO₂ emissions from material production, accounting for process emissions, direct use of fossil fuels, and the electricity and heat use accounted with the average emission factors over total electricity and heat production, grow less than energy use, as renewable energy gains a larger share of the energy mix during the century. In the LMD scenario, material production CO₂

emissions decline throughout the century without any active abatement, being only 1.1 Gt yr⁻¹ in 2100, or 15% of the 2020 level; driven particularly by the declining cement and steel production volumes and increased secondary material production. Cumulatively, the CO₂ emissions from material production are 80% smaller in the LMD than in SSP5, and 65% smaller than in SSP2.

For HANPP, we calculate a low-end estimate based solely on the amount of harvested biomass (Haberl *et al* 2014) (i.e. not including NPP losses due to land conversion), which grows in each scenario, but in very different degrees. As food demand, which is the main driver of human land-use, was kept constant across the scenarios, all observed differences arise from the wood harvested for pulp and logwood, and from bioenergy use to satisfy the changing industrial energy-use across the scenarios. Even if the harvest-based estimate is lower than some other ways of measuring HANPP, this implies a 10% appropriation of all terrestrial NPP during the latter part of the century in the LMD scenario, and over 20% appropriation in 2100 in SSP5. This shows that the development of future material use of our society can have drastic impact on the whole Earth's ecosystem. Changes in food demand towards more plant-based

diets, which were not explored here, could provide an even stronger lever for reducing HANPP (Erb *et al* 2024).

The amount of final waste generated also differs considerably across the scenarios and reacts to changes to material production volume with a lag, as discussed in relation to figure 3. The modelled final waste increases until 2060 in all the scenarios, and doubles from current levels to 12 Gt yr⁻¹ even in the LMD scenario, due to the large material stock existing already. From SSP1 to SSP4 the growth is slow during the latter half of the century, but increases strongly in SSP5, growing nearly eightfold from 2020 to 2100. A large part of the final waste is concrete, rock and sand from retired buildings, roads and other infrastructure.

4. Discussion

Growing material stocks and production volumes are key challenge for climate change mitigation (Krausmann *et al* 2020) especially because material producing industries are often seen as 'hard to abate' sectors (Edelenbosch *et al* 2024). Therefore, understanding the potential future material stock and flow

dynamics has high relevance for tackling the environmental pressures from material production. By bridging industrial ecology and material stock-flow modelling with integrated assessment models, this work contributes to building a framework for assessing the resource basis of future economies and identifying leverage points for sustainability transitions.

Our quantification of economy-wide material stocks and flows in the SSP and LMD scenarios is based on a top-down approach using historical material stock intensities of the global economy (Krausmann *et al* 2017a, 2020) and the GDP projections of the SSP scenarios. As this is a mathematical identity, any alternative futures require alternative assumptions for either component. The total stocks' partitioning to end-uses and further to main materials continued existing long-term trends, and we tested our scenarios' sensitivity to variations in the end-use breakdown. From here, material production and waste flows can be calculated using material lifetime dynamics, herein based on a simplified materials module derived from the detailed MISO2 model (Wiedenhofer *et al* 2024a), yielding a physically consistent representation of stocks by end-use and material, as well as production and waste volumes of each material. With this calculation built into the SuCCESs IAM, our work is one contribution to bridging across the MFA and IAM domains (Pauliuk *et al* 2017, Lefèvre 2024).

We find that strong economic growth without notable reductions in material stock intensity would lead to significant increases in material stocks, production and waste. Without active mitigation efforts, these would lead to significant increases in environmental pressures, e.g. in raw materials extraction, appropriation of nature, CO₂ emissions and waste accumulation, contributing to pollution of land and water. Substantial reductions in stock intensity and slower economic growth, as portrayed in our LMD scenario, might be enabled by demand-side solutions and low-carbon lifestyles (Sugiyama *et al* 2024), as well as a more circular economy (Wiedenhofer *et al* 2025). These could tap the potential for avoiding GHG emissions, material resource extraction and waste generation (Creutzig *et al* 2024, Guan *et al* 2025), and reduce climate Paris Agreement-compliant strategies' reliance on CO₂ removal (Edelenbosch *et al* 2024) and other feasibility constraints (Brutschin *et al* 2021).

More broader drivers of change and deliberate actions to mitigate the environmental pressures are obviously possible and should be investigated in the future. We did not vary the shares of end-use stocks or the material shares of each end-use by narrative, but only through the uncertainty analysis, and these shares might change over time through structural

change of the global economy and material substitutions, for example. Structural changes (e.g. digitalization) could also facilitate lower material intensity, increased material efficiency by reducing losses in the production phase, longer lifetimes of end-use stocks and increased recycling of waste to secondary products (Pauliuk *et al* 2024, Schandl *et al* 2024). Outside the material system, CO₂ emissions can be reduced through technological change incentivized by climate policy, while substitution between materials in certain end-uses (such as timber in construction) and across raw materials sources (such as biomass replacing fossil feedstocks for plastics) could facilitate the transition towards sustainability (e.g. Siljander and Ekholm 2018, Mattlar and Ekholm 2025). All these elements could be captured in future studies with models combining MFA and IAM approaches, as was done here.

Beyond the climate problem, rising material production over the century will require growing extraction of different minerals (Schandl *et al* 2018), from sand and rock for building basic infrastructure to rare earth elements extracted for modern technology. While food production is the main contributor for the human appropriation of nature (Haberl *et al* 2014), our scenarios demonstrated also significant effect on HANPP over different scenarios of material production. Societies will also be generating a growing stream of waste, which should be increasingly directed to secondary material production following the principles of the circular economy. This development means overcoming several challenges in social metabolism (Haas *et al* 2020). Waste flows will consist mostly of more inert strains like rock and concrete, but with significant amounts of more problematic materials, like plastics (Geyer *et al* 2017).

These environmental challenges come as the flipside of consumption. While growing production and consumption have long been seen as measures of increasing welfare, discussion on long-term futures have incorporated perspectives of sufficiency as one lever for the sustainability transition (Sugiyama *et al* 2024, Wiedenhofer *et al* 2024b). What should be further explored is alternative developments of economic structures and the nature of economic output in the future, and the impact of this on the required material stocks, energy use and environmental impacts (Lefèvre 2024). The production of both physical and intangible products will require both energy and physical material stocks, but in different quantities. While our sensitivity analysis scratched this surface by varying the shares of different end-uses of the total material stock, addressing this question in a more structured and justified way could be an important endeavour to deepen the SSP storylines further.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17378393> (Ekholm 2026).

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References

- Bauer N *et al* 2017 Shared socio-economic pathways of the energy sector—quantifying the narratives *Glob. Environ. Change* **42** 316–30
- Bolt J and van Zanden J L 2024 Maddison-style estimates of the evolution of the world economy: a new 2023 update *J. Econ. Surv.* **39** 631–71
- Brutschin E, Pianta S, Tavoni M, Riahi K, Bosetti V, Marangoni G and Van Ruijven B J 2021 A multidimensional feasibility evaluation of low-carbon scenarios *Environ. Res. Lett.* **16** 064069
- Creutzig F *et al* 2024 Demand-side strategies key for mitigating material impacts of energy transitions *Nat. Clim. Change* **14** 561–72
- Deetman S, Marinova S, van der Voet E, van Vuuren D P, Edelenbosch O and Heijungs R 2020 Modelling global material stocks and flows for residential and service sector buildings towards 2050 *J. Clean. Prod.* **245** 118658
- Edelenbosch O Y *et al* 2024 Reducing sectoral hard-to-abate emissions to limit reliance on carbon dioxide removal *Nat. Clim. Change* **14** 715–22
- Edwards A, Brockway P E, Bickerstaff K and Nijse F J M M 2025 Towards modelling post-growth climate futures: a review of current modelling practices and next steps *Environ. Res. Lett.* **20** 053005
- Ekholm T 2026 Results for the manuscript 'Exploring global, economy-wide material trajectories and associated environmental pressures under shared socioeconomic pathways' *Zenodo* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17378393>)
- Ekholm T, Freistetter N C, Rautiainen A and Thölix L 2024 CLASH—climate-responsive land allocation model with carbon storage and harvests *Geosci. Model Dev.* **17** 3041–62
- Ekholm T, Freistetter N-C, Matlar T, Schaber T and Rautiainen A 2025 SuCCESs—a global IAM for exploring the interactions between energy, materials, land use, and climate systems in long-term scenarios (model version 2024–10-23) *Geosci. Model Dev.* **18** 4805–22
- Erb K H, Matej S, Haberl H and Gingrich S 2024 Sustainable land systems in the Anthropocene: navigating the global land squeeze *One Earth* **7** 1170–86
- Geyer R, Jambeck J R and Law K L 2017 Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made *Sci. Adv.* **3** e1700782
- Grubler A *et al* 2018 A low energy demand scenario for meeting the 1.5 °C target and sustainable development goals without negative emission technologies *Nat. Energy* **3** 515–27
- Guan Y, Shan Y, Hang Y, Nie Q, Liu Y and Hubacek K 2025 Unlocking global carbon reduction potential by embracing low-carbon lifestyles *Nat. Commun.* **16** 4599
- Haas W, Krausmann F, Wiedenhofer D, Lauk C and Mayer A 2020 Spaceship earth's odyssey to a circular economy—a century long perspective *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **163** 105076
- Haberl H, Erb K H and Krausmann F 2014 Human appropriation of net primary production: patterns, trends, and planetary boundaries *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* **39** 363–91
- Haberl H, Wiedenhofer D, Pauliuk S, Krausmann F, Müller D B and Fischer-Kowalski M 2019 Contributions of sociometabolic research to sustainability science *Nat. Sustain.* **2** 173–84
- Hertwich E G 2021 Increased carbon footprint of materials production driven by rise in investments *Nat. Geosci.* **14** 151–5
- Hickel J, Brockway P, Kallis G, Keyßer L, Lenzen M, Slameršak A, Steinberger J and Ürge-Vorsatz D 2021 Urgent need for post-growth climate mitigation scenarios *Nat. Energy* **6** 766–8
- IIASA 2024 SSP scenario explorer 3.0 (available at: <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ssp/>)
- Kermeli K, Edelenbosch O Y, Crijns-Graus W, van Ruijven B J, van Vuuren D P and Worrell E 2022 Improving material projections in integrated assessment models: the use of a stock-based versus a flow-based approach for the iron and steel industry *Energy* **239** 122434
- Krausmann F, Wiedenhofer D, Lauk C, Haas W, Tanikawa H, Fishman T, Miatto A, Schandl H and Haberl H 2017a Global socioeconomic material stocks rise 23-fold over the 20th century and require half of annual resource use *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* **114** 1880–5
- Krausmann F, Schandl H, Eisenmenger N, Giljum S and Jackson T 2017b Material flow accounting: measuring global material use for sustainable development *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* **42** 647–75
- Krausmann F, Wiedenhofer D and Haberl H 2020 Growing stocks of buildings, infrastructures and machinery as key challenge for compliance with climate targets *Glob. Environ. Change* **61** 102034
- Lamb W F *et al* 2021 A review of trends and drivers of greenhouse gas emissions by sector from 1990 to 2018 *Environ. Res. Lett.* **16** 073005

- Lefèvre J 2024 Integrated assessment models and input–output analysis: bridging fields for advancing sustainability scenarios research *Econ. Syst. Res.* **36** 675–98
- Magalar L, Verdolini E and Szklo A 2026 Unlocking circular economy policies in integrated assessment models *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **225** 108614
- Mattlar T and Ekholm T 2025 The impact of bioplastics production on climate change mitigation, fossil fuels and land-use *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **212** 115234
- O'Neill B C *et al* 2017 The roads ahead: narratives for shared socioeconomic pathways describing world futures in the 21st century *Glob. Environ. Change* **42** 169–80
- Pauliuk S, Arvesen A, Stadler K and Hertwich E G 2017 Industrial ecology in integrated assessment models *Nat. Clim. Change* **7** 13–20
- Pauliuk S, Carrer F, Heeren N and Hertwich E G 2024 Scenario analysis of supply- and demand-side solutions for circular economy and climate change mitigation in the global building sector *J. Ind. Ecol.* **28** 1699–715
- Popp A *et al* 2017 Land-use futures in the shared socio-economic pathways *Glob. Environ. Change* **42** 331–45
- Riahi K *et al* 2017 The shared socioeconomic pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: an overview *Glob. Environ. Change* **42** 153–68
- Schandl H *et al* 2018 Global material flows and resource productivity forty years of evidence *J. Ind. Ecol.* **22** 827–38
- Schandl H *et al* 2024 Global material flows and resource productivity: the 2024 update *J. Ind. Ecol.* **28** 2012–31
- Schandl H, Lu Y, Che N, Newth D, West J, Frank S, Obersteiner M, Rendall A and Hatfield-Dodds S 2020 Shared socio-economic pathways and their implications for global materials use *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **160** 104866
- Siljander R and Ekholm T 2018 Integrated scenario modelling of energy, greenhouse gas emissions and forestry *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Change* **23** 783–802
- Soergel B *et al* 2024 Multiple pathways towards sustainable development goals and climate targets *Environ. Res. Lett.* **19** 124009
- Stegmann P, Daioglou V, Londo M, van Vuuren D P and Junginger M 2022 Plastic futures and their CO₂ emissions *Nature* **612** 272–6
- Streeck J, Veléz-Henao J, Kikstra J S, Jihoon M, Krausmann F and Pauliuk S 2025 Small increases in socioeconomic material stocks can secure decent living standards globally *Nat. Sustain.* **8** 1567–81 accepted
- Sugiyama M *et al* 2024 High with low: harnessing the power of demand-side solutions for high wellbeing with low energy and material demand *Joule* **8** 1–6
- Ünlü G, Maczek F, Min J, Frank S, Glatter F, Natsuo Kishimoto P, Streeck J, Eisenmenger N, Wiedenhofer D and Krey V 2024 MESSAGEix-Materials v1.1.0: representation of material flows and stocks in an integrated assessment model *Geosci. Model Dev.* **17** 8321–52
- Vélez-Henao J A and Pauliuk S 2023 Material requirements of decent living standards *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **57** 14206–17
- Wiedenhofer D, Streeck J, Wieland H, Grammer B, Baumgart A, Plank B, Helbig C, Pauliuk S, Haberl H and Krausmann F 2024a From extraction to end-uses and waste management: modeling economy-wide material cycles and stock dynamics around the world *J. Ind. Ecol.* **28** 1464–80
- Wiedenhofer D *et al* 2024b Industry transformations for high service provisioning with lower energy and material demand: a review of models and scenarios *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* **49** 249–79
- Wiedenhofer D, Wieland H, Leipold S, Aoki-Suzuki C, Watari T, Aguilar-Hernandez G A and Streeck J 2025 The circular economy and climate change: the state of national and global evidence on mitigation potential *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* **50**
- Zhou C, Elshkaki A and Graedel T E 2018 Global human appropriation of net primary production and associated resource decoupling: 2010–2050 *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **52** 1208–15